

FORMATION OF THE LIFE SKILLS OF THE STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETITIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. In the world around us, mathematics is involved in all our activities. In recent years, interest in learning foreign languages, especially English, has increased dramatically. This can be explained by the desire of the young generation to study in prestigious foreign universities, learn the experience of leading foreign countries and use them in the development of various sectors of their country. In this article, we will discuss with you how to work with graphs, charts, and tables given in the "IELTS Academic Writing Task" of the IELTS exam.

Keywords: IELTS, diagram, graph, table, pie chart.

Task 1 of the IELTS Academic Writing Task asks test-takers to describe some data (graph/table/diagram) and provide a summary of that data in their own words. Depending on the proposed task, the abilities of the examinees are evaluated as follows:

- Organize, present and possibly compare data
- describe the steps of a process or procedure
- describe an object or event or sequence of events
- explaining how something works.

Assignments include a brief explanation of the diagram (table, graph, process). It is necessary to identify, compare and analyze the main characteristics. For this, in turn, the student's knowledge of the "Statistics and Probability" section, which is one of the mathematics sections, is important. Ability to gather, read, represent, and analyze diagrams related to real-world situations.

When doing research or presentations, it is easier for the audience to use a diagram to organize and categorize the information.

When analyzing the diagram, the reader should ask himself the following questions:

1. In which form of the diagram is the information given.
2. What are the units of measurement? (Length, weight, quantity, time, area, volume)
3. What time intervals were considered?
4. What information can be obtained from the given?
5. What are the main characteristics (properties)?
6. Are there similarities and differences?

Let's analyze the task below (Activity tool).

The charts show the reasons why people cycle or drive to work. Analyze the data, summarize it according to its main characteristics and compare it if necessary.

The reason for going to work by bicycle

Velosipedda ishga borish sabablari

The reason for going to work by car

Avtotransportda ishga borish sabablari

We are given two pie charts. The charts show the percentages of reasons why people choose to cycle or drive to work, according to a survey.

The following information can be obtained from those given.

1. In the first diagram, the majority of people said that they ride bicycles for their health and to avoid pollution.

2. In the second chart, the highest percentage of people stated that they commute to work for convenience.

It is noteworthy that almost equal number of participants answered "Faster than a car" and "Faster than a bicycle" in the survey. The distance from home to work is taken into account.

In the first chart, 30% of people said they cycle to work for their own health and environmental protection. In the second diagram, 40% of respondents stated that they travel by car for convenience. At the same time, an almost equal number of participants believe that moving in their own vehicle is faster.

30% of the participants said that cycling is beneficial for health, 30% that it does not pollute the environment, 15% that there is no problem with parking, 13% that it is possible to save the economy, 12% that the distance to work is close and that you don't get stuck in traffic. as a basis.

According to the answers given by the participants of the second group, 40% consider car transport to be comfortable, 21% consider it to work long distances, 14% and 11% think it is faster and better than a bicycle, and 14% think that the style of clothing is appropriate for traveling in a car.

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